

From the vision to the implementation of sustainable energy solutions: technology, business and people

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Abstract

Ensuring current and future energy needs for dynamic economies and highly demanding societies raises environmental concerns. Smart grids put together renewable-based generation, demand response, distributed storage, and electric vehicles able to bring new solutions able to significantly reduce the environmental impact of traditional electrical energy generation and energy use. However, the actual use of such resources in an intensive way, poses new technical and business challenges to the power and energy sector.

The keynote addresses the current and envisioned solutions for the management of these distributed energy resources, enabling the implementation of sustainable energy solutions in the frame of a user-centric and market driven approach for smart grids and electricity markets. Enabling sustainable generation, transaction, and use of electrical energy, requires this user-centric approach and the participation of individual consumers and citizen energy communities. As energy generation becomes intensively distributed and based on renewable-based resources, consumers and citizen communities are empowered in terms of the way they produce, transact, and use energy. However, this is a difficult transition as consumers do not have the required knowledge and resources to cope with their new opportunities and responsibilities in the energy field.

Artificial intelligence based approaches are crucial to enable that transition, namely because they provide the required methods to model the human behaviour, to support decentralized decision-making, and to provide the players and the systems with adaptive approaches able to cope with real-time constraints, incomplete and uncertain information.

MARTINE (Multi-Agent based Real-Time INfrastruture for Energy), a platform to support real-time energy management and simulation of buildings and smart grids, will be described. The platform will be used as the basis to present different data-driven and cognitive approaches to support efficient energy management in buildings and smart grids.

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